

GEOLOGICAL STRUCTURE AND HISTORY OF THE WEST ANTARCTIC IN THE LIGHT OF PREVIOUS STUDIES. PROSPECTS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE FEATURE UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC RESEARCH

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Complex tectonic processes that date back to the Paleozoic era have formed the geological structure of West Antarctica, particularly the Antarctic Peninsula and the South Shetland Islands, as we know it now. Long-term subduction along the Pacific margin of Gondwana has had a huge impact on the regional geology. It has led to the accretionary complexes and magmatic arcs formation. Then, in the late Paleozoic – early Mesozoic, West Antarctica was influenced by two orogenies – the Gondwanide and Chonide events. They were driving forces for crustal deformation and magmatism processes. The Bransfield Strait, which is a close object to Vernadsky station, is a back-arc basin formed as a result of extensional processes that took place after the end of subduction processes near the South Shetland Trench. According to geological reconstructions, it is now suggested that either the Antarctic Peninsula or Patagonia were part of a single continental block, and they have started to separate from each other after the Gondwana break-up. Gravity and magnetic data from the Bransfield Basin indicate significant structural segmentation and tectonic activity in this region, accompanied by rifting and magmatic intrusions development. It is important to study the geological past of this region because it is a great area to understand subduction dynamics and continental margin evolution.

We have decided to dedicate our feature research to the interpretation of geologic history and geodynamics of the Western Antarctic using magnetic parameters of igneous rocks. Before this specialized part of the work, we have to understand the geological structure and history of the region as it is known today.